

HU: Ritah partners of breastfeeding women

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Edited by: Super

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Codes-quotations list

Code-Filter: All [69]

Code: • Acquire knowledge about the baby {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:10 [t is helpful. Sometimes she ge..] (42:42) (Super)

Codes: [• Acquire knowledge about the baby]

t is helpful. Sometimes she gets knowledge of things she did not know of yet may be helpful to the baby.

Code: • Acquire knowledge on studies {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:14 [She gets to learn a lot of thi..] (68:68) (Super)

Codes: [• Acquire knowledge on studies]

She gets to learn a lot of things.

Code: • Advise women to go to health facility {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:3 [I don't believe in those cultu..] (11:11) (Super)

Codes: [• Advise women to go to health facility]

I don't believe in those cultural practices. I would have believed in them it was in the other ancient era because then our mothers could use them and could give birth even without visiting a Health Facility but lately, the herbs used are not authentic. Today, a breastfeeding mother upon conceiving has to go to a Health facility and follow the medical personnel's guidance.

Code: • Affects adherence to drugs {3-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:7 [Not taking their medication on..] (27:27) (Super)

Codes: [• Affects adherence to drugs]

Not taking their medication on time.

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:10 [First and foremost, she can fo..] (34:35) (Super)

Codes: [• Affects adherence to drugs]

First and foremost, she can forget swallowing.

It may result to poor pill time taking. For example she is hiding it, she does not want you to know she is meant to swallow at 9am. Am still around by 9am, I have not moved a step out. Then she cannot swallow on time because she has never disclosed to me. She may be like let me wait him to leave that sometimes I have left at 11am,.At that time you leave, it can affect the drug efficacy.

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:10 [It affects her adherence if sh..] (36:36) (Super)

Codes: [• Affects adherence to drugs]

It affects her adherence if she does not disclose. She may not swallow her medication well or even infecting the baby. She may be given a specific interval for breast feeding a woman yet the man needs her to breastfeed otherwise.

Code: • counselling {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:15 [First and foremost,, I have to..] (48:48) (Super)

Codes: [• counselling]

First and foremost,, I have to ensure that she gets what she is supposed to get right from looking after her, encouraging her, counselling her that when she adheres well our child will be fine.

Code: • Depends on the relation; some could refuse participation {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:18 [It depends on the way you co-r..] (64:64) (Super)

Codes: [• Depends on the relation; some could refuse participation]

It depends on the way you co-relate with your partner there may be misunderstandings in the home that sometimes women pick un wanted information in those studies with may lead to domestic violence. So your partner can be against these studies to block you from going there

Code: • Encourage her to adhere to medicines {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:16 [I have encouraged her to follo..] (52:52) (Super)

Codes: [• Encourage her to adhere to medicines]

I have encouraged her to follow the medical practitioner's guidelines. For her to do whatever he is doing with a lot of carefulness not to affect the child's health at that moment.

Code: • Extreme corners cupboards {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:9 [In most cases you find that wo..] (29:30) (Super)

Codes: [• Extreme corners cupboards] [• Under the bed]

In most cases you find that women stay alone in the home yet the partner reports home late in the night. The woman has a big advantage to hide medication away from the partner. Sometimes we come home tired when you just need to take supper and sleep off.

The strategies are many...She can get a rare place you rarely visit for example under the bed more so at the extreme corner of the bed yet it's easier like on a side board. Or probably she can have a small handbag where she hides the medicine where you cannot suspect

Code: • Fear for marriage break up {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:8 [Fear for marriage break up. Mo..] (29:29) (Super)

Codes: [• Fear for marriage break up]

Fear for marriage break up. More so splitting marriage secrets in the community.

Code: • Fear of the outcome {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:8 [In most cases women have that ..] (26:26) (Super)

Codes: [• Fear of the outcome]

In most cases women have that fear. The most important thing is you're bonding at home the way you relate. If that close relationship is limited that fear to disclose occurs. There is also an illness that is hard to disclose but it depends on the foundation you built at the start of the relationship. That foundation is key for a smooth relationship.

Code: • Financial challenges {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:6 [Financial challenges. This is ..] (21:21) (Super)

Codes: [• Financial challenges]

Financial challenges. This is a big challenge that sometimes you have a breastfeeding woman who has financial needs but when you the husband cannot provide. That alone leads you to worry because you want to provide but there is no money.

Code: • financial support {6-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:5 [She has to tell me being his h..] (20:20) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support]

She has to tell me being his husband. I have to know her stand for example She may be given medication to be taken by both of us which may need a doctor's review after a month which may turn out to be worse calling for a man's financial support. So if you're not prepared financially, it may cause your break up

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:8 [Medical support. That in case ..] (29:29) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support]

Medical support. That in case you have some money, it's better you transport her or board transport means together and visit the health facility to get knowledge of her medication/treatment and what needs to be done.. Even if your not financially well, still its compulsory for you to go to a health facility to hear from the medical personnel's.

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:2 [Buying them the needful.] (11:11) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support]

Buying them the needful.

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:3 [Probably if the woman is not y..] (14:14) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support]

Probably if the woman is not yours. But if the woman is yours...why not support her. That is impossible.

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:4 [They support them through taki..] (15:15) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support]

They support them through taking care of them because whenever she is supported or whether you seat her down and show her the benefits of breast feeding for example it builds her immunity, the child rarely falls sick etc than that one who is not breast fed etc. She gets to see the importance after all it's so important on the baby's side to breastfeed her the recommended way.

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:3 [Giving the mother care and bas..] (14:14) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support]

Giving the mother care and basic needs.

Code: • financial support to attend the hospital visits {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:5 [For you to remind her not to f..] (20:20) (Super)

Codes: [• financial support to attend the hospital visits]

For you to remind her not to forget about her medication.

Code: • Focus on study participation {2-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:16 [In case she has come for a stu..] (65:65) (Super)

Codes: [• Focus on study participation]

In case she has come for a study, for her to pick content on the subject matter that brought her. Not to catch up with information that was out of the subject matter.

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:1 [It depends on the food she fee..] (6:6) (Super)

Codes: [• Focus on study participation]

It depends on the food she feeds on e.g. I usually see her using millet or soya to get breast milk.

Code: • Get knowledge for mother and baby {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:17 [It's very good for them to par..] (56:56) (Super)

Codes: [• Get knowledge for mother and baby]

It's very good for them to participate in studies since there are many things they do not know. They know less about children. So when they get that future knowledge pertaining children, a child can be well natured.

Code: • Go to the Health Facility and talk to a health worker for supportive disclosure. {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:14 [In case any strange disease di..] (47:47) (Super)

Codes: [• Go to the Health Facility and talk to a health worker for
supportive disclosure.]

In case any strange disease discovered in her, this would need to be sorted out from a Health facility for proper guidance

Code: • Good explanation from the partner explaining the situation and the partner should listen {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:13 [In case a woman has a medical ..] (45:45) (Super)

Codes: [• Good explanation from the partner explaining the situation and
the partner should listen]

In case a woman has a medical challenge and has to disclose to a partner, she can be supported when she elaborates her

disease clearly then the man helps with adherence when he embarks on strict adherence following the health worker's advice.

Code: • handbags {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:9 [Keeping their medication in a ..] (32:32) (Super)

Codes: [• handbags]

Keeping their medication in a secret place yet men rarely check their property say their handbags since men leave home early for work.

Code: • Hide medicines with relatives {2-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:9 [Women have a lot of tactics...re..] (32:32) (Super)

Codes: [• Hide medicines with relatives]

Women have a lot of tactics...reason being us men tend not to be at home, you get home late and tired so.. You find when the woman has already taken her pills which you're unaware of. So in this scenario women hide a lot from us for us not to be in the know. Sometimes they keep their medication with relatives, sometimes takes the medication out of the house being that the house is small. A man can do cleaning of the house and lands on that medication then the marriage gets disorganized.

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:11 [It leads to poor adherence whe..] (39:39) (Super)

Codes: [• Hide medicines with relatives]

It leads to poor adherence where in most cases it's not timely e.g. when your partner has not travelled that day when one was meant to swallow in the morning say at 9am but now, it's where your partner is seated, you find yourself taking it at 1pm or not swallowing at all because you don't want your partner to quiz you on the medication your swallowing.

Code: • I cannot refuse her from participating in a study. {2-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:13 [I cannot refuse her from parti..] (43:43) (Super)

Codes: [• I cannot refuse her from participating in a study.]

I cannot refuse her from participating in a study.

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:15 [Since am fully responsible on ..] (56:56) (Super)

Codes: [• I cannot refuse her from participating in a study.]

Since am fully responsible on her, I have to be in the know of what is going on.

Code: • I sign the partner consent form after checking the details of the study {2-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:21 [I cannot refuse signing that f..] (70:70) (Super)

Codes: [• I sign the partner consent form after checking the details of
the study]

I cannot refuse signing that form but I need to know the details on it.because I cannot just sign since the wife is going for research. I need to first get the details for me to sign what I have understood as a partner then I allow her.

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:22 [It can benefit both of us. Ano..] (76:77) (Super)

Codes: [• I sign the partner consent form after checking the details of the study]

It can benefit both of us.

Another thing, since she is breastfeeding, it can help her know how to handle that breast feeding process.

Code: • If the couple has a good relationship with each other {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:8 [It needs when the partner is y..] (34:34) (Super)

Codes: [• If the couple has a good relationship with each other]

It needs when the partner is yours but if the person is a bit distant, it's a little hard .With your partner you can sort it out.

Code: • It can lead to domestic violence if not conducted well {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:7 [In most cases, women take medi..] (26:26) (Super)

Codes: [• It can lead to domestic violence if not conducted well]
[• People don't disclose for protective reasons]

In most cases, women take medication stealth fully without disclosing it to their partners. That cuts across both sides a man can do it and also a woman can but in most cases that's a woman's habit to their co wives. A woman can do it for protective purposes which can be misinterpreted by the husband. It can even lead to domestic violence at home.

Code: • It is good, that women acquire knowledge {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:17 [These studies are good. She ge..] (55:55) (Super)

Codes: [• It is good, that women acquire knowledge]

These studies are good. She gets to learn a lot of things on her side and the baby for example how to feed the baby well plus you yourself, you learn how to treat yourself during the 9 months pregnancy

Code: • It is good, that women acquire knowledge. {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:11 [The good in it being that late..] (39:39) (Super)

Codes: [• It is good, that women acquire knowledge.]

The good in it being that lately, we date young mothers 17 years, She can come to visit a health worker little knowing that when breastmilk pours/drops in a child's ear, it's dangerous. But when the health worker explains it to her, she then understands it.

Code: • It is not easy due to fear of the results {2-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:15 [That is not an easy thing it c..] (50:50) (Super)

Codes: [• It is not easy due to fear of the results]

That is not an easy thing it can culminate into problems because you may freely come from wherever and disclose to your partner who may treat you negatively since you did not test together yet sometimes he may also be having his

health challenges. In such a scenario, both sides need to understand each other's medical condition since both of them may be in hiding yet you may find that the one they disclosed to may even have gone faster on treatment than the wife and probably the cause of the wife's infection yet partner is proving to be harsh to the wife.

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:12 [In most cases it's not that ea..] (41:41) (Super)
Codes: [• It is not easy due to fear of the results]

In most cases it's not that easy to disclose such an issue just like that. But in most cases it depends on the mutual understanding you have with your partner at home. If you relate well with your partner regardless of the challenges, it depends on the way you handle your partner

Code: • Lack of funds to support with family needs {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:6 [Sometimes there are no funds /..] (21:21) (Super)
Codes: [• Lack of funds to support with family needs]

Sometimes there are no funds /no money which breeds hatred in them since the demands may be many.

Code: • Love for the partner {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:6 [Probably because she loves you..] (22:22) (Super)
Codes: [• Love for the partner]

Probably because she loves you yet you're staying together. But also, there are those who keep quiet about it.

Code: • Maintain a balanced diet to acquire breastmilk {2-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:1 [She has to follow Health worke..] (6:6) (Super)
Codes: [• Maintain a balanced diet to acquire breastmilk]

She has to follow Health worker's instructions. She has to feed on body building foods, foods that help in milk secretion for her body to be energetic. For example, rice, posho, fruits,etc. as per the health worker's guidance.

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:1 [First and foremost, a woman ha..] (6:6) (Super)
Codes: [• Maintain a balanced diet to acquire breastmilk]

First and foremost, a woman has to be taking porridge to help in milk secretion plus feeding well on silver fish ,offals,some soups and being taken care of well. That can help her.

Code: • Men are harsh and could domestically abuse the women {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:6 [Harshness from the partner's s..] (22:22) (Super)
Codes: [• Men are harsh and could domestically abuse the women]

Harshness from the partner's side. Men are harsh, they don't want to listen to what their partners are talking.

Code: • Men way the benefit against the risk to make a decision {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:20 [We need to first weigh the ben..] (68:68) (Super)

Codes: [• Men way the benefit against the risk to make a decision]

We need to first weigh the benefits of what she is going to participate in. If it's a research, there is no way I can refuse.

Code: • Motivation and encouragement {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:11 [First and foremost they need p..] (37:37) (Super)

Codes: [• Motivation and encouragement]

First and foremost they need positive encouragement/motivation while showing them the good in adhering well daily and timely. That if she adheres well the child's health won't be compromised and you the mother this helps your general wellbeing to be healthy and energetic to breast feed the child well.

Code: • Motivation to take medicines while breastfeeding {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:3 [That is good since it is a for..] (12:12) (Super)

Codes: [• Motivation to take medicines while breastfeeding]

That is good since it is a form of motivation to her and you show her the good in breastfeeding. So if you don't encourage her that much, the baby may not get the required nutrients from the mother.

Code: • Not necessary to refuse women to participate {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:11 [For women not participating...I ..] (45:45) (Super)

Codes: [• Not necessary to refuse women to participate]

For women not participating...I depends, people's hearts are different but it's not necessary for one to refuse a woman to participate in a study

Code: • Nutritional support {2-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:3 [In case there is something she..] (13:13) (Super)

Codes: [• Nutritional support]

In case there is something she needs in the breast feeding season, provide it. For example you had provided the porridge but she tells you the porridge is lacking milk, provide the milk.

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:4 [Buying them essentials at home..] (17:17) (Super)

Codes: [• Nutritional support]

Buying them essentials at home. If a person has what to use at home, food is there and porridge she benefits from them.

Code: • Partner cannot support you if unaware of the situation {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:7 [When the woman fails to disclo..] (24:24) (Super)

Codes: [• Partner cannot support you if unaware of the situation]

When the woman fails to disclose the medical challenge she is experiencing...That can be risky because your partner cannot know the situation you're going through. Yet if you disclose it to him and he gets to know, he can support you

with adherence. Let it be on the man's side on medication when the wife is aware, the situation becomes easier. Even the way he handles you is different from the other one whose medical challenge he is not aware of.

Code: • People don't disclose for protective reasons {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:7 [In most cases, women take medi..] (26:26) (Super)

Codes: [• It can lead to domestic violence if not conducted well]
[• People don't disclose for protective reasons]

In most cases, women take medication stealth fully without disclosing it to their partners. That cuts across both sides a man can do it and also a woman can but in most cases that's a woman's habit to their co wives. A woman can do it for protective purposes which can be misinterpreted by the husband. It can even lead to domestic violence at home.

Code: • Provide financial support for transport {2-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:18 [First and foremost, to allow h..] (61:61) (Super)

Codes: [• Provide financial support for transport]

First and foremost, to allow her that if she does not have transport, you provide it to her to go participate in research.

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:19 [It is a mutual agreement from ..] (63:63) (Super)

Codes: [• Provide financial support for transport]

It is a mutual agreement from the two of you because even if you decide as a woman, you may insist and go participate but when the husband was not in agreement with it. Your mind won't be settled like it would have been when you had agreed properly.

Code: • Psychological support from partner {2-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:7 [That is bad. My thought could ..] (27:27) (Super)

Codes: [• Psychological support from partner]

That is bad. My thought could be for the mother to disclose to the partner that she is on medication because when the partner is aware of it, he also becomes supportive.

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:8 [Women fear for the fact that t..] (29:29) (Super)

Codes: [• Psychological support from partner]

Women fear for the fact that the partner may have never taken initiative to test before then the mother tests first so... When the woman tests herself, she may fear to disclose to the partner, then she comes back and takes her medication without the man's knowledge since the woman knows her status.

Code: • Reminders to take meals on time {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:10 [I personally used to remind my..] (36:36) (Super)

Codes: [• Reminders to take meals on time] [• Reminders to take medicines.]

I personally used to remind my partner to swallow the medication given to her from the Health facility even when I was not near her, I could ask whether she first fed on something before swallowing , whether she had got any

improvement ever since she started swallowing it.

Code: • Reminders to take medicines. {2-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:10 [I personally used to remind my..] (36:36) (Super)

Codes: [• Reminders to take meals on time] [• Reminders to take medicines.]

I personally used to remind my partner to swallow the medication given to her from the Health facility even when I was not near her, I could ask whether she first fed on something before swallowing, whether she had got any improvement ever since she started swallowing it.

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:7 [After getting to know of it, y..] (30:30) (Super)

Codes: [• Reminders to take medicines.]

After getting to know of it, you have to remind her to go and get medication.

Code: • Spouse has to inform the partner about participation {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:13 [You definitely allow her to pa..] (61:61) (Super)

Codes: [• Spouse has to inform the partner about participation]

You definitely allow her to participate in the study.

Code: • Spread the disease to baby {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:11 [She may infect the baby when s..] (37:37) (Super)

Codes: [• Spread the disease to baby]

She may infect the baby when she breastfeeds with sores on the breasts.

Code: • Support her to maintain hygiene for both mother and baby {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:4 [It has to be a dual process fo..] (13:13) (Super)

Codes: [• Support her to maintain hygiene for both mother and baby]

It has to be a dual process for one reason or the other because hygiene is key. She has to be extra clean while breastfeeding for the child's immunity not to be compromised that even before breastfeeding she has to first clean the breast for the baby to feed from a clean place without picking harmful bacteria.

Code: • Suspicious about the studies {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:18 [Those who do not participate t..] (58:59) (Super)

Codes: [• Suspicious about the studies]

Those who do not participate tend to claim that they have not got approval from their partners. Some just get suspicious of what will be there and the outcomes.

Code: • Take a nutritious diet {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:1 [Eating healthy mostly...and with..] (6:7) (Super)

Codes: [• Take a nutritious diet]

Eating healthy mostly...and with less stress/thoughts.

Taking porridge.

Code: • Take woman to hospital for the healthcare to aid disclosure {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:9 [My advice to say my sister can..] (32:32) (Super)

Codes: [• Take woman to hospital for the healthcare to aid disclosure]

My advice to say my sister can be like....Go to the Health Facility and talk to a health worker for supportive disclosure. He/she can drive the point home appropriately.

Code: • The bad I see in it mostly, is that a breastfeeding mother may come in those studies and pick bad habits /ideas from fellow breastfeeding mothers. {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:12 [The bad I see in it mostly, is..] (40:40) (Super)

Codes: [• The bad I see in it mostly, is that a breastfeeding mother may come in those studies and pick bad habits /ideas from fellow breastfeeding mothers.]

The bad I see in it mostly, is that a breast feeding mother may come in those studies and she picks bad habits /ideas from fellow breast feeding mothers who may be older than her or her age mates. Forexample there can be a conversation from another woman who may confirm forexample that sincerely the baby am carrying is not for my real husband...which habit she can adopt. They may have bad conversations, eg, giving birth to men who are not their real partners, ideas of extra marital affairs, it can be financial support where your husband is not providing financially since it's a habit for women to show off that they are best. A woman can be like when I gave birth, my husband gave me a car, a phone, yet people are different.

Code: • They don't allow breastmilk to drop on the baby {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:2 [While breast feeding they don'..] (7:7) (Super)

Codes: [• They don't allow breastmilk to drop on the baby]

While breast feeding they don't want the breastmilk to drop/pour on the baby.

Code: • They take porridge for breast milk secretion. {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:1 [They take porridge for breast ..] (6:6) (Super)

Codes: [• They take porridge for breast milk secretion.]

They take porridge for breast milk secretion.

Code: • Treatment buddies to remind them take medicines {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:12 [Encourage them to swallow thei..] (42:42) (Super)

Codes: [• Treatment buddies to remind them take medicines]

Encourage them to swallow their medication per the doctor's instructions because if not followed one may either affect the baby's or her life.eg when the doctor advised you to take your medication at 8:30am then you swallow at 9am.

Code: • Trustworthy in the relationship {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:19 [It's all about trustworthiness..] (71:71) (Super)

Codes: [• Trustworthy in the relationship]

It's all about trustworthiness for one to get involved in something when your partner is in the know. This brings about that mutual agreement between the 2 of you. It may not be that important where you getting involved in that study is not compulsory.

Code: • Under the bed {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:9 [In most cases you find that wo..] (29:30) (Super)

Codes: [• Extreme corners cupboards] [• Under the bed]

In most cases you find that women stay alone in the home yet the partner reports home late in the night. The woman has a big advantage to hide medication away from the partner. Sometimes we come home tired when you just need to take supper and sleep off.

The strategies are many...She can get a rare place you rarely visit for example under the bed more so at the extreme corner of the bed yet it's easier like on a side board. Or probably she can have a small handbag where she hides the medicine where you cannot suspect

Code: • When the relationship is unstable {3-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:5 [In most cases, it stems from t..] (18:18) (Super)

Codes: [• When the relationship is unstable]

In most cases, it stems from the way you relate at home. This is so important because whenever you do not relate well many things go astray which in turn affects the baby.

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:5 [The breast feeding woman may b..] (20:21) (Super)

Codes: [• When the relationship is unstable]

The breast feeding woman may be mistreating the partner due to the ongoing situation. They may not be relating well at home.

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:6 [The challenges they may be goi..] (24:24) (Super)

Codes: [• When the relationship is unstable]

The challenges they may be going through may not be the important thing. As long as he has money he can offer support anywhere.

Code: • Woman cannot travel without the spouse approval {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:21 [The consent automatically come..] (77:77) (Super)

Codes: [• Woman cannot travel without the spouse approval]

The consent automatically comes from home first for the woman to get approval to participate in a study because she cannot just travel without the partner's knowledge.

Code: • Women acquire new knowldege {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:16 [First and foremost whenever a ..] (51:51) (Super)

Codes: [• Women acquire new knowldege]

First and foremost whenever a breastfeeding woman engages in studies, you broaden the mind, you get to learn new ideas and that you did not know of.

Code: • Women acquire new knowledge {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:17 [We have to accept them to part..] (54:54) (Super)

Codes: [• Women acquire new knowledge]

We have to accept them to participate in such studies to enable her understand more the good in breast feeding children, the good in adhering while breast feeding. For her mind to be informed.

Code: • Women are unhygienic, men separate beds or run away from home {1-0}

P 3: PBFW 3 240221-0013.rtf - 3:5 [That can happen but... there is ..] (18:18) (Super)

Codes: [• Women are unhygienic, men separate beds or run away from home]

That can happen but... there is no where I have ever seen i.e. cannot give evidence on it but on many occasions, men don't like staying with women who have children since some children tend to be get dirty which may not be okay with the man which leads to separation of items like beddings that after giving birth, the wife gets her side of sleeping and also the man gets his. For the fact that the child needs more attention hygienically but am not part of those men since I know that whole system, the woman needs a helping hand during that moment. We help one another.

Code: • Women demand more support than the partner's financial ability {1-0}

P 1: PBFW 1 240219-2315-1.rtf - 1:4 [Sometimes breast feeding mothe..] (16:16) (Super)

Codes: [• Women demand more support than the partner's financial ability]

Sometimes breast feeding mothers may request for more than your (financial input-ennyingizaayo) eg. Milk for porridge she consumes, a cup of milk can cost 1000 shs daily, sometimes the baby has to feed on porridge with milk in the morning hours then breastfeeds in the night that sometimes it becomes hard to balance the mother's needs and your (financial intake-ennyingiza).

Code: • Your partner should be your friend {1-0}

P 2: PBFW 2 240220-0003.rtf - 2:9 [It needs when someone is your ..] (38:38) (Super)

Codes: [• Your partner should be your friend]

It needs when someone is your real friend. because for my case my partner is HIV negative so we went to together to the Health Facility. The good things, our children are grown up so,,, we gave up on those child birth issues.

Code: both partners should participate {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:19 [It would have been better for ..] (66:66) (Super)

Codes: [both partners should participate]

It would have been better for the male partner to also go and participate in research since you get to know of that knowledge together. The upbringing of the child can be better even the home can be nice.

Code: depends on the relationship between the couple {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:15 [It may take 2 categories... If y..] (49:49) (Super)

Codes: [depends on the relationship between the couple]

It may take 2 categories... If you relate well, it becomes easier but if you don't relate well with your partner that much, it becomes hard on the mother's side to disclose. Violence sets in.

Code: Encourage people in the community to participate to add to new research knowledge {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:23 [First and foremost, the resear..] (81:81) (Super)

Codes: [Encourage people in the community to participate to add to new research knowledge]

First and foremost, the researches are not bad, they are good and whenever you learn and add something new to your brain you are different from that one who has not learnt since you can go back to the community and teach your fellow women on that you have benefited.

Code: generate new evidence in the population {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:23 [It helps in rising the child w..] (85:85) (Super)

Codes: [generate new evidence in the population]

It helps in rising the child well and for the mother herself to get that knowledge of sustaining the baby well.

Code: i have supported my partner since we are both HIV positive {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:16 [I do support my partner since ..] (51:51) (Super)

Codes: [i have supported my partner since we are both HIV positive]

I do support my partner since we got each other when we were both HIV positive so we know one mother.

Code: no known mthys, beliefs and practices during breastfeeding {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:2 [I cannot comment on that becau..] (10:10) (Super)

Codes: [no known mthys, beliefs and practices during breastfeeding]

I cannot comment on that because I have no idea about it.

Code: partner should participate too {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:22 [Me I would recommend that man ..] (81:81) (Super)

Codes: [partner should participate too]

Me I would recommend that man to allow her go and participate in research because you never know what she is knowledgeable of and that she has no knowledge of

Code: right to disclose is when the couple is relaxed and children are asleep {1-0}

P 4: PBFW 4 240221-0048.rtf - 4:14 [he right time is that time whe..] (46:46) (Super)

Codes: [right to disclose is when the couple is relaxed and children are asleep]

he right time is that time when you're taking supper because in most cases most children then are asleep when you're alone or during bed time since the bedroom time is the marriage court since during this moment, a person's brain then is settled with no phone distractions. Yah

Code: when the couple is alone {1-0}

P 5: PBFW 5-240221-0116.rtf - 5:14 [It needs when you're together ..] (46:46) (Super)

Codes: [when the couple is alone]

It needs when you're together just the 2 of you probably home resting, then he tells you the problem since he may not be in position to tell it to an outsider. He may prefer you the partner.
